

Agroforestry Suitability Tool User Guide

Agroforestry encompasses a set of practices where trees and shrubs are intentionally integrated into agricultural and animal systems, such as in alley cropping, riparian buffers, silvopasture, and windbreaks (USDA). As interest in agroforestry grows, practitioners, policymakers, and researchers need effective tools to identify regions where agroforestry practices can be most effectively targeted. This Agroforestry Suitability Tool aims to guide stakeholders, such as researchers and practitioners, in identifying areas where resources for agroforestry expansion will likely have the greatest impact.

The Agroforestry Suitability Tool allows users to define criteria for modeling agroforestry suitability for different agroforestry practices across the US Midwest. The tool allows users to specify which criteria they would like to include in the model and how they weigh the relative importance of each criterion in decision-making. Users may run the model for the entire 12-state Midwest region or specific states, counties, or watersheds.

Funding

North-Central SARE Award GNC22-344 and USDA Hatch Award 7003617.

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Features

- Agroforestry practices covered in this tool: alley cropping, silvopasture, riparian buffers, and windbreaks.
- Select variables and weights for each criterion to fit specific goals.
- Consider different criteria: tree growth suitability, environmental priorities, social feasibility, and economic viability.

Limitations

- The tool is designed primarily for high-level planning and not intended for farm-level agroforestry decisions. Additional information on the farm biophysical parameters and farmer goals is necessary to make farm-level decisions.
- Not all variables are relevant for all regions. For example, some tree species may not be relevant for agroforestry in all Midwestern states.
- Note: Run times may be long for large spatial extents.

Practice Definitions and Potential Areas

Purpose: Identify lands currently in use for annual crops or livestock/grassland where agroforestry practices could be targeted. The Agroforestry Suitability Tool (AST) allows users to generate suitability maps for each of the following four agroforestry practices:

Alley Cropping

*Definition*¹: Planting rows of trees and shrubs with crops in between the rows. May also refer to intercropping or multi-functional perennial polycultures, where trees are integrated in crop fields without defined rows.

Data used to define relevant land areas:

Data was compiled from the 2022 Cropland Data Layer². Alley cropping areas are any lands currently in annual crops or pasture/grassland (i.e., on all agricultural lands).

(Image: Alley cropping fruit trees, woody perennials, and timber trees. Sarah Castle)

Riparian Buffers

*Definition*³: Trees and shrubs that are planted adjacent to streams and other waterways.

Data used to define relevant land areas:

The potential areas for riparian buffers are the 30-meter buffer around waterways, as defined by the National Hydrography Dataset flowlines layer⁴, and on agricultural lands according to the Cropland Data Layer².

(Image: Riparian buffer along stream on a silvopasture operation. Alexandra Ramirez)

¹ <https://www.fs.usda.gov/nac/practices/alley-cropping.php>

² USDA National Agricultural Statistics Service Cropland Data Layer, Year, Published crop-specific data layer [Online]. Available at <https://nassgeodata.gmu.edu/CropScape/> (accessed 09/18/23). USDA-NASS, Washington, DC

³ <https://www.fs.usda.gov/nac/practices/riparian-forest-buffers.php>

⁴ U.S. Geological Survey, 2022, National Hydrography Dataset (ver. USGS National Hydrography Dataset Best Resolution (NHD) for Hydrologic Unit (HU) 4 - 2001 (published 20191002)), accessed January 28, 2024 at URL <https://www.usgs.gov/national-hydrography/access-national-hydrography-products>

Silvopasture

Definition⁵: A system that has trees/shrubs and grazing livestock integrated on the same land.

Data used to define relevant land areas: Silvopasture was restricted to only grazing lands (pasture/grassland) as defined by the Cropland Data Layer².

(Image: Silvopasture cattle grazed in pine tree system. Sarah Castle)

Windbreaks

Definition⁶: trees and shrubs planted on the edges of fields, creating a barrier against wind.

Data used to define relevant land areas: The potential areas for windbreaks are the 10-meter buffers on the edges of fields as defined by the USDA Crop Sequence Boundaries dataset⁷.

(Image: Windbreaks along the edge of annual crop fields. Alexandra Ramirez)

⁵ <https://www.fs.usda.gov/nac/practices/silvopasture.php>

⁶ <https://www.fs.usda.gov/nac/practices/windbreaks.php>

⁷ Hunt KA, Abernethy J, Beeson P, Bowman M, Wallander S, Williams R, 2023. Crop Sequence Boundaries (CSB): Delineated Fields Using Remotely Sensed Crop Rotations.

Criteria for Determining Suitability of Practices

The AST predicts agroforestry practice suitability based on four indicators: 1) environmental priorities, 2) tree growth suitability, 3) social feasibility, and 4) economic viability, which were created using relevant sets of variables, as described below.

Users can select the weights to attach to each of these four indicators when calculating overall agroforestry suitability.

1. Environmental Priorities

Environmental priority areas were determined by normalizing and weighing four environmental criteria: soil erosion by water⁸, soil erosion by wind⁹, water quality^{10,11} and soil organic carbon potential¹². Water quality is estimated using the combination of surface and groundwater quality, and the user has the option to consider each separately or as a combined water quality indicator.

Environmental Priorities Default Weights: Default weights for the environmental priority criteria were retrieved from the NRCS Conservation Practice Physical Effects Rating (CPPER). The CPPER assigns the relative benefit each agroforestry practice has to address an environmental concern using an integer of -5 to 5, where -5 indicates substantial worsening of an outcome, 0 has no effects, and 5 has substantial improvements for a given outcome¹³.

Users can select the weights for each variable and select which variables to include (by setting unwanted variables to zero weight)

2. Tree Growth Suitability

Nine tree species that are commonly used for agroforestry systems in the Midwest are available to include in the analysis: black walnut, chestnut, apple, eastern cottonwood,

⁸ Borrelli P, Ballabio C, Yang JE, Robinson DA, Panagos P. GloSEM: High-resolution global estimates of present and future soil displacement in croplands by water erosion. *Scientific Data*. 2022;9(1):406.

⁹ Walkinshaw M, O'Geen AT, Beaudette DE. Soil Properties. California Soil Resource Lab. <https://casoilresource.lawr.ucdavis.edu/soil-properties/2022>

¹⁰ United States Environmental Protection Agency. EnviroAtlas. Nitrate violation index - Groundwater. Retrieved: 09/18/23, from <https://epa.gov/enviroatlas>

¹¹ United States Environmental Protection Agency. EnviroAtlas. Nitrate violation index – Surface water. Retrieved: 09/18/23, from <https://epa.gov/enviroatlas>

¹² Peralta G, Di Paolo L., Luotto I, Omuto C, Mainka M., Viatkin K, Yigini, Y, 2022. Global soil organic carbon sequestration potential map (GSOCseq v1.1) - Technical manual. Rome, FAO.

¹³ USDA, 2024. Conservation Practices Physical Effects (CPPE) - National Template. Retrieved: 09/18/23, from <https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/resources/guides-and-instructions/conservation-practice-physical-effects>

white oak, common persimmon, hazelnut, sycamore, and pecan. Requirements for tree growth (climate, soil, and topographic variables) were identified using the CABI Forestry Compendium¹⁴ and the USDA Plant Database¹⁵. The dataset used to define tree species suitability were derived from USDA-NRCS SSURGO and STATSGO soil datasets^{9,16,17,18}, the USGS 3DEP elevation dataset¹⁹, and Oregon State’s PRISM monthly spatial climate dataset²⁰ to create suitable growth regions for each species.

Tree Growth Suitability Default Weights: Weights for each tree species suitability are equal, and all nine tree species are included in the indicator by default.

Users can select different subsets of tree species to include in the model.

- Note: Agroforestry–relevant tree species are typically not relevant west of the 100th meridian (e.g., North Dakota, South Dakota, Nebraska, and Kansas), users should be aware of this when using the app—drought-tolerant species are needed west of the 100th meridian.

3. **Social Feasibility**

The social feasibility indicator is a county-level indicator of the predicted social acceptability of agroforestry. The social feasibility indicator is generated using five variables from the USDA National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) 2022 Agricultural Census. The variables include: 1) the rate of acres set-aside for conservation areas (e.g., conservation easements or government programs like Conservation Reserve Program), 2) the rate of rented land operations, 3) the rate of rotational grazing, 4) operations operated by new/beginning farmers (<11 years on any operation), and 5) the reported number of hired labor.

¹⁴ CABI. CABI Compendium. Wallingford, UK: CAB International; 2024. Retrieved: 09/18/23, from <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/>

¹⁵ USDA NRCS, 2024. The PLANTS Database (<http://plants.usda.gov>, 02/29/2024). Greensboro, NC USA: National Plant Data Team.

¹⁶ Soil Survey Staff, NRCS, USDA, 2023. Soil Survey Geographic (SSURGO) Database for USA Drainage Class. <https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=55d0c2d32c234ce497cd30dc9bc06729>

¹⁷ Valayamkunnath P, Barlage M, Chen F, Gochis DJ, Franz KJ. Mapping of 30-meter resolution tile-drained croplands using a geospatial modeling approach. *Scientific Data*. 2020;7(1):257

¹⁸ Soil Survey Staff, NRCS, USDA, 2023. Soil Survey Geographic (SSURGO) Database for USA Frost Free Period. <https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=edd2f5723d3a47df9c71ac8ddb8f277>

¹⁹ U.S. Geological Survey, 2023. 3D Elevation Program 10-Meter Resolution Digital Elevation Model.

²⁰ Daly C, Smith JI, Olson KV. Mapping Atmospheric Moisture Climatologies across the Conterminous United States. *PLOS ONE*. 2015;10(10):e0141140

Social Feasibility Default Weights: The five social feasibility variables were normalized and combined using a weighted sum. The default weights for each variable are equal (1).

Users can select the weights for each variable and select which variables to include (by setting unwanted variables to zero weight).

- Note: Social criteria (county-scale data) are not meaningful for county or watershed level analyses and are not visible if this analysis scale is selected.

4. **Economic Viability**

The economic viability indicator was calculated using county-level data on producers' average net cash farm income per acre (from the NASS 2022 Agricultural Census) and the SSURGO National Commodity Crop Productivity Index (NCCPI) to estimate the relative profitability of current systems. The suitability indicator is an inverse relationship to current profitability, such that areas that have the lowest current profitability are the most suitable for agroforestry, i.e., agroforestry needs to be relatively less economically competitive to surpass the current system.

Economic Viability Default Weights: This indicator only uses one variable, so there are no relevant weights. The current system profitability is normalized and inversed to generate the indicator.

- The economic suitability parameter was adjusted to have an inverse assumption option.

Additional Resources

Below we provide links to additional resources for agroforestry practice standards, programs that support agroforestry, and tree suitability.

Canopy COMPASS Tool: <https://www.canopycompass.com/>

Expanding Agroforestry Project: <https://www.nature.org/en-us/what-we-do/our-priorities/provide-food-and-water-sustainably/expanding-agroforestry-production/>

NRCS Agroforestry Practice Standards: <https://www.fs.usda.gov/nac/practices/conservation-practice-standards.shtml>

Savanna Institute: <https://www.savannainstitute.org/>

The Center of Agroforestry (University of Missouri): <https://centerforagroforestry.org/>

For further information on how the variables and indicators were selected and calculated, please contact Sarah Castle at saraheb3@illinois.edu for access to the full paper.

Step-by-step Guide

To use the tool, follow these instructions:

- 1) Access through the following link:
<https://agroforestrymap.projects.earthengine.app/view/agroforestry-suitability-tool>
- 2) Select state or region of interest
 - a. Region (all the Midwest)
 - b. State
 - c. County
 - d. Watershed
- 3) Select agroforestry practice.

Note: you can only select one practice at a time and changing the practice resets all inputs to the default weights (which have different defaults for each practice)

 - a. Alley cropping
 - b. Riparian buffer
 - c. Silvopasture
 - d. Windbreaks

Agroforestry Suitability Tool

This tool generates estimates of priority areas for expanding agroforestry in the US Midwest based on environmental, social, and economic criteria. This panel allows users to define input parameters for estimating agroforestry social-ecological suitability. All parameters are set to default parameters, which may be adjusted according to users needs and priorities.

We do not recommend this tool for parcel-level decisions, which require additional field-level social and biophysical data. This tool may take several minutes to generate results as it runs your analysis in real time.

[Access the user guide here.](#) (Opens in new tab.)

Region of Interest Required 2

Select Region Type

Select the region for which you would like to run your analysis. You may run your analysis for the entire US Midwest region or for a specific state, county, or watershed. To select a county or watershed, you must input the state in which it is located first. Watersheds that cross state bounds will be included in their entirety. NOTE: Large regions may take several minutes to show results since your analysis is being run in real time.

Select Agroforestry Practice Required 3

Select a Practice

Select only ONE agroforestry practice for current analysis. NOTE: Changing the practice automatically changes the advanced settings to practice-specific defaults (if changing advanced settings, need to set them after selecting practice and change them each run).

Set Indicator Weights Click for instructions 4

(This image represents steps 2-4).

4) Set indicator weights (see above for category descriptions).

These weights are scaled as 0-5, 0 having no importance and 5 having highest importance. For example, if the tree growth suitability is weighted as 5 and other variables are weighted as 2, the tree growth indicator will be weighted 2.5x higher than any of the other three indicators in the suitability map.

By default, these indicators are equally weighted (1). To omit an indicator from your analysis, set the weight to zero (0).

- a. Environmental priority areas weight
- b. Tree growth suitability weight
- c. Social feasibility weight
- d. Economic viability weight

(These images represent steps 4 and 5)

5) Advanced settings: when clicked, a new input panel will appear on the right side of the current text box. The advanced settings allow users to specify the variables and weights used to generate the four indicators from step 4.

The sub-category variables are used to generate the indicator (e.g., wind erodibility, water erosion, soil organic carbon potential, and water quality are the

variables used to generate the environmental priority areas indicator). The weights are only relative to the other variables used to create the indicator (and are not relative to other indicator variables). To omit an indicator from your analysis, set the weight to zero (0).

a. Environmental priority area indicator variables.

Sliders allow the user to select the weights for each variable in calculating the environmental priority indicator. Default weights are automatically generated based on the selected practice.

- Soil organic carbon sequestration potential index
- Water erosion index
- Wind erodibility index
- Ground water quality index
- Surface water quality index
 - a. Checkbox: Combine ground and surface water quality to use as an overall water quality indicator. Default: checked, to avoid overweighting water quality.

b. Select tree species.

The tree growth suitability indicator is the number of the selected tree species that are suitable for a given area, e.g., if nine species are selected, the model will give a higher suitability to areas that can grow more of the nine species.

c. Social feasibility indicator variables.

Sliders allow the user to select the weights for each variable in calculating the social feasibility indicator. Default weights are equal for all variables (value of 1).

- Long term conservation practice index
- Rotational grazing practice index
- Rented land index
- New/beginning farmers index
- Hired labor

6) Once all criteria have been chosen, click **RUN** to see the results. **Note:** The program is running in real time and should take no more than 5 minutes to complete. If you are running a large analysis (e.g., entire Midwest), it could take up to about 20 minutes.

7) After you **RUN** the program, a legend will appear that will allow you to interpret the results. Purple indicates areas with the lowest suitability for the agroforestry

practice, and yellow indicates areas with the highest suitability for the agroforestry practice.

- 8) If you want to view the indicator layers in addition to the overall suitability later, click on layers in the top right corner. A drop-down menu of different layers will appear allowing you to toggle the preferred layer.

The sliders allow you to adjust the visibility of the layers that are toggled on. Each of the indicator layers is normalized on a scale of 0-1, with yellow indicating highest suitability (1) and purple indicating lowest suitability (0).

(This image represents steps 7 and 8)